

‘Vrikshayurveda’ in Sanskrit Literature : An Observation in the Context of Traditional Knowledge

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Ancient Indian tradition considered nature as living object. The cordial relationship between human being and the nature was found narrated in the entire range of Sanskrit literature. Therefore, the flora and fauna played important role in their life. Although there were no separate systematic works on plant science in Vedic period, there are however innumerable references in this regard. The Rigveda (X.97.3) mentioned the different types of plants on morphological ground. The Atharvaveda (VIII.7.1) classified medicinal plants on the basis of their colour. The different parts of the plants are described systematically in the Taittiriya Samhita (VII.3.19.1) and Vajasaneyi Samhita (XXII.28). The Mahabharata (12.184.17) mentions that the plants have feeling of joys and sorrows and hence it is said that hurting of plants is a sin indeed. The Manusamhita states the same in this regard. Thus scientific messages in this field are scattered in various works. Letter on applied science on plants has been presented in some works which are known as Vrikshayurveda i.e. the knowledge of tree life. This science is also called as Bhesajavidya as the major portion of the medicinal substances are taken from the plants. Some remarkable independent works in this field are Vrikshayurveda by Parashara, Vrikshayurveda by Surapala, Vrikshayurveda section in the Agni Purana, Vrikshayurveda section in the Brihatsamhita and Vrikshayurveda section in Sarngadhara-samhita. Moreover, some Puranas also contain materials in this regard. A comparative study of these works can be done which will suggest optimal, holistic agricultural and gardening system. The Vrikshayurveda deals with the taxonomy, classification and selection of soils, plant propagation techniques, plant nourishment, plant diseases etc. Nowadays, use of fertilizer and chemicals stands as a challenge to our life. The traditional knowledge in this regard is highly needed to meet the sustainable utilization of plants. Therefore, an effort has been made to focus the importance of messages narrated in the Vrikshayurveda to establish a healthy way in modern agriculture.

Keywords : Vrikshayurveda, Rigveda, Atharvaveda, Plant Science, Agriculture.